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DIVERSITY AND INCLUSION RESEARCH IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION: WHAT HAS CHANGED IN THE LAST 10 YEARS?

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RATIONALE

“Diversity has an increasingly large part to play in the more globally oriented technical industry in bringing a sense of balance between several groups of personnel e.g. in gender, age, cultural background. These enterprises focus on better possibilities of recruiting, a long-term staff retention and a target group oriented product development for a better positioning at the market. Engineering education, however, works with a kind of mono-cultural recruiting, standardised learning offers for all students and a more general oriented product development and technical research.” The former challenge for engineering education was put forward by Susanne Ihsen and Xiangyun Du in the Special Issue on Diversity concepts and experiences in Engineering Education of the European Journal of Engineering Education in 2009.

In our workshop we will jointly explore how the scholarship around diversity and inclusion in engineering education has evolved since and which additional research methodologies have been applied related to diversity and inclusion.

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The workshop has **four particular goals**:

1. introducing to each of the participants four different papers exemplary for methodologies or case studies for research on diversity and inclusion in engineering education.
2. community building: each participant is challenged to collaborate with new colleagues in the engineering education field
3. identifying opportunities of diversity and inclusion research for practice and for new research
4. exploring the (dis)advantages of joint paper-reading

PARTICIPANT ENGAGEMENT

The workshop is built on the successful workshops' formats that the SEFI Engineering Education Research and the Gender and Diversity Special Interest Groups have been running at the previous conferences. By joint paper reading and discussing in small groups using a jig-saw format, participants will explore the evolution of diversity and inclusion engineering education research in the last 10 years. Participants will be challenged to work in diverse groups with people they have not yet beforehand to enhance the community building aspect of the workshop. A plenary closing discussion will summarize good practices and formulate priorities for the next decade.

TAKEAWAY

The attendees will have gained insight in the evolution of the research in diversity and inclusion in the last 10 years. On top of detailed knowledge of four recent publications they obtain a list of further literature. Participant conclusions will be made available online after the session on the SEFI SIG websites.